

An Examination of Investment Decision-Making Behavior during Pre-Covid-19 Pandemic and New Normal with Reference to Tricity (Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali)

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Abstract : COVID-19 pandemic's impact on the global economy, this approach is now more critical than ever. Investors' preferences shifted dramatically during previous crises, which had a direct impact on investors investing decisions and the value of businesses. The study aims to investigate the global pandemic's effect on investors investing decisions in Tricity (Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali). The study employed a random sample technique, and the primary data was acquired, which was completed by 225 people. SPSS software ascertains mean, standard deviation, and ANOVA analysis. The findings indicate a significant impact of covid-19 on the investors investing decisions and demographic, as well as the psychological factors of the investors also impact their investing decisions.

Keywords : Covid -19, Tricity, Global Economy, Investors' Preferences, Pandemic.

1. Introduction

COVID-19 pandemic's impact on the global economy, this strategy is now more critical than ever. Investors' preferences shifted dramatically during previous crises, which had a direct impact on stock prices and the value of businesses. The selection of the period for the investigation was not without its significance.

The technique is now more important than ever because the COVID-19 pandemic influences the global economy. Company values have fluctuated in prior crises as investors' preferences moved dramatically.

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Putting money into anything with the expectation of earning a return at a later date is known as an investment. In today's world, there are many uses for money. Several options exist for people who want to put their money somewhere, such as "gold/silver, insurance, public provident funds, equity shares, mutual funds, gold/silver, real estate, and national pension schemes." The investments that individuals feel the safest and most confident making are in bank savings and public provident funds, whereas the ones that people feel are the most successful are stock investments. Throughout the past several years, India's economy has been performing exceptionally well for the nation. The focus of this study is on how investors act when they have a lot of different investment options.

When a new and contagious disease named COVID-19 first appeared in Wuhan, China, in the early 2020s, it had a devastating impact on the economies of several countries. The economic crisis triggered by the Coronavirus is distinct from previous financial crises in terms of its cause, scope, and intensity (Ding et al., 2020). That is why experts worldwide are starting to pay attention to how much money is being made from this COVID-19 outbreak.

"The Securities and Exchange Board of India" (SEBI) and other regulatory bodies in India have simplified the process of investing in mutual funds and initial public offers (IPOs) through the use of "unified payment interfaces" (UPIs) to encourage this phenomenon (SEBI, 2020). Investors typically have a variety of reasons for participating in a particular investment opportunity. After COVID-19, it is more important than ever to understand the motivations of investors so that positive investment trends can continue. Investor preferences can be influenced by a variety of factors, including age and gender, according to several studies.

As of the end of December 2019, China had reported many cases of COVID-19, which was later found to be a unique member of the coronavirus family. The global stock market was the first casualty of this pandemic. In early February 2020, Iraq became the third country to report a case affecting all commercial and financial activity. Even the most secure economies of developed nations have been rattled by this outbreak (Sun et al., 2021). However, it revealed the long-standing inequities in financial regulation. Globally, it had a detrimental impact on financial markets due to countries' efforts to curb it.

Regarding regulating the current global crisis, investors' positive behavior and financial market regulation by the regulatory body was among the most crucial factors (Lee, 2020). The emerging coronavirus pandemic, SARS-CoV-2, has

produced unprecedented economic disruptions (Arfah et al., 2020). There are at least two key variations this time around. First and foremost, its effects on the economy have been bigger than those of any other natural catastrophe in the past four decades. The global economy has reached a standstill due to the viral containment measures. Several policy instruments and methods are employed by governments around the world in the event of a fiscal crisis. Tools and techniques that can help include human safety, fiscal policy, macro prudence, and monetary policy.

Because to COVID-19, the past several weeks have been challenging for the economy of the entire world and the financial markets. Even while there are still chances to profit from the present pandemic, most investors are facing portfolios painted in red due to the Coronavirus spreading to every continent except Antarctica. During economic booms, traditional investing tactics have been well-investigated and documented. Despite this, there are just a few studies on investing during an epidemic.

1.1. Low-Risk Investment During the COVID-19 Pandemic

➤ Government Securities Fund

Investing in government securities funds is advantageous on a fundamental level because the government ensures the return of investor cash. The Reserve Bank of India provides Gilt mutual fund schemes on the government's behalf. These investments are often kept to maturity and have a long-term horizon. Because of its liquidity and tax advantages, it outperforms other debt investments regarding after-tax returns.

➤ Index Fund

An index fund attempts to mimic a financial market index by holding various stocks and bonds. An index fund, rather than a specific stock or bond, allows you to participate in the whole market. Mostly, they are low-risk investments that provide superior total returns to other mutual funds. Having a cheaper administration charge than actively managed funds, passively mutual funds also have an added benefit.

➤ Liquid Mutual Funds

Investing in fixed-income assets like Treasury bills, treasury bonds, and commercial paper is what liquid mutual funds do best. The short maturity time of these open-ended plans makes them an excellent short-term investment

alternative because they provide a modest rate of return (3-6 months). Withdrawals from liquid funds can be completed within 24 hours following the end of the working day if there is no lock-in period. Liquid funds benefit from not imposing a penalty upon withdrawal or breakage. It is a smart strategy to invest spare cash because it broadens your investment horizons.

➤ **Post office Monthly scheme**

The post office's monthly investment plan is a great option for people looking for a long-term investment. Only a 5-year lock-in term and an upper limit (INR 4.5 lacs) prevent an individual from investing in this outstanding investment, which boasts significant interest and monthly payouts. Most cannot compete with India's modest monthly income plan from the Indian post office for safety, promptness of payment, and a low-risk financial commitment.

➤ **Gold**

Non-corrosive metal has served as the gold standard for economies around the world since ancient times. As a low-risk investment, Gold's price is less affected by market fluctuations and corrects itself more quickly. Investments in Gold can provide a safety net and a sense of security, even for those who take on a lot of risk with their money. Global lockdowns have served to raise Gold's price. In addition to gold ETFs and national gold bonds, there are numerous ways to invest in gold mutual funds and ETFs. Regardless of how diversified or selective an individual's investment strategy may be, each has unique qualities that make it suitable for all investors.

1.2. An Overview of the Investment Avenues

In India, there are a variety of investing options. The following are summaries of the various investment options:

➤ **Marketable investment**

"Equity shares," "Preference shares," "Convertible debentures," "Nonconvertible debentures," "bonds of public sector entities," "savings certificates," "Government securities," and other forms of debt are all examples of marketable investments. They may be exchanged for money as well. Most people who wish to invest their money often put it into public stocks and bonds.

➤ **Non-Marketable Investment**

"Bank deposits" and "insurance policies" are illiquid investments. Fixed deposits, such as the "National Saving Certificate (NSC)," the "Kisan Vikas Patra

(KVC),” private firm shares, etc., are also included. Many people have investments they can’t get rid of because they aren’t marketable. Regarding frequency and significance, regular and permanent deposits at post offices and savings banks are at the top.

➤ **Mutual fund**

Instead of buying financial assets on their own, people can invest in mutual funds. Mutual funds give investors a way to spread out the risk of their money by investing in various types of assets. People who work for fund managers decide where to invest, how much to invest, and when to sell so that the mutual fund’s scheme can make money for its investors, which is what they do.

1.3. Empirical Studies on Investors’ Investing Decision of Tricity

An economy and an organization’s financial well-being depend on it. This is especially true when investing in the stock market, where there is much ambiguity regarding future outcomes. In the world of traditional finance, investors are seen as rational. Securities are always priced properly and equitably by rational investors who have uniform expectations in terms of securities, Fama’s (1965) efficient market hypothesis theory. In the realm of finance, behavioral finance is a new paradigm. It aims to comprehend and foresee the systemic financial market implications for mental decision-making. It uses economic and psychological factors to help people make better financial decisions (Olsen, 1998). Traditional financial theories are unable to explain and manage numerous market abnormalities. Behavioral finance theories can be used to solve these abnormalities.

According to Statman (2011), most people’s investment decisions are impacted by other people’s choices. To offer a sense of what investors want, let’s suppose they want to make a lot of money, retire comfortably, and do well in their native country. By doing this, we can better understand what causes price swings in the financial markets. Because of this insight, active stock market investors have expanded outside the realm of the dominant investment banks.

2. Literature of Review

Bieliaieva et al. (2020) analyzed the current business state and showed that internal disruptions within companies might cause a crisis earlier than for the entire country or world economy. Rather than focusing on short-term solutions, their article focuses on the long-term consequences of crisis management on a

company's sales and earnings. The pandemic necessitated firms to adapt quickly to current trends, such as e-commerce, to avoid being shut down. It was also notable that the cost of a crisis extends far beyond the scope of individuals and families and into the realms of nations and even the entire planet.

Gormsen & Koijen (2020) examined how investors' expectations of economic improvement beyond the confines of the current crisis and subsequent governmental responses might be calculated using information from the accumulating equities market and payout futures.

Okhuese (2020) concluded that until a vaccination against COVID-19 was developed, the number of people afflicted may continue to rise. As a result, coronavirus infections and deaths have risen due to increased economic illiquidity and general deterioration. Restrictive laws and lockdowns have contributed significantly to financial market stability, as has a general drop in public opinion regarding the disease.

Ramelli, S., & Wagner, A. F. (2020) tested the effect of the "COVID-19 pandemic" on corporate "stock prices" in the United States. They determined that the epidemic led to extraordinarily negative and erratic aggregate market reactions. Significantly lower cumulative abnormal returns were found for firms with greater exposure to China and a higher share of international revenues.

Senthamizhselvi, A & Vedantam, SR (2018) stated that "Bank deposits," "insurance," "PPF," "NSC," "Post office," "Gold," and "Chit funds" all have a big impact on investment decisions, especially when people investing in high- or low-risk options. This helps people make better decisions when they are investing.

Mak, KY & Lp, WH (2017) analyzed the study of investors' financial investing behavior and discovered that elements including socioeconomic status, psychological make-up, and demographics like gender, marital status, and prior investment experience all had an impact on investors' choices. This requires financial service providers to establish appropriate strategic plans that consider different investors' preferences.

Maini (2017) explained that unpredictable market prices were a major factor in the decisions of individual investors. Most of the decisions made by the Tehran Stock Exchange were based on politics and emotions because there were not enough financial experts.

Raman et al. (2017) stated that Individual investors who need to think more about how to improve their investment choices were the goal of the study. Investors choose the right path based on their commonality, level of confidence, and the stages of their lives.

Bakar & Yi (2016) added that Investors overestimated their market knowledge because they thought they had much experience. They were more concerned about protecting their principal investment than making money than they were about making money. They also thought that the psychological factors that affect their decision-making depended on the gender of the investors.

Katabi, R. & Dimoso, R. (2016) conducted a study in Tanzanian; investment decision strategies were influenced by elements such as the industry in which the firm operates, increased sales, commercial business, number of staff, and the form of business.

Riyazahmed & Saravanaraj (2016) analyzed that investor qualities such as herd mentality and mental accounting have a key role in determining investment preferences, as do other behavioral factors. Sheepishness is when an investor follows the crowd's lead in purchasing or selling a stock. An investor's subjective valuation of an amount of money based on factors such as its origin and intended use is an example of a cognitive bias known as "mental accounting."

Abdallah & Hilu (2015) found that determinants explain the impact of the degree of income and regularity of income of individual investors on their financial behavior. Three potential independent variables that could influence investor risk attitude include investors' judgments of information asymmetry, investor perceptions, and overconfidence. The study also highlights aspects affecting financial behavior and builds a similar investment pattern.

Horn et al., (2015) Although genuine alternatives have been extensively covered, it is surprising that they would not be used more frequently. Only 7% of the top corporations in Norway, Denmark, and Sweden employ real options, whereas 74% use NPV, according to a recent poll of 1500 CFOs. Real options concepts and their complexity seem to be the fundamental barriers to execution.

Lee et al. (2015) compared investor preferences for short-term vs. long-term investments in a comparative study. Short and long-term investments were the focus of the study. Investing in financial assets with the expectation of generating gains shortly or selling them for a large profit would be known as short-term investing.

Nurullah, M. & Kengatharan, L. (2015b) suggested that the population comprised 285 publicly traded companies in Dhaka, Bangladesh (DSE). The data collection questionnaire was adapted from a previous foundational study in the field. Companies with the highest market capitalization were sent surveys. For this reason, the DSE100-indexed companies were selected. Through email, the company's CFO and director of finance received surveys. Using the official DSE website and the company's websites, email addresses were obtained. Only seven companies responded to the initial call for participation. Emails were addressed to all remaining companies, and the Chartered Accountants Association assisted in this effort and received 46 responses from 100 companies, or 46% of them.

Vijaykumar (2015) emphasized the importance of tax advantages and ease of acquisition while deciding on an investment path. An investment opportunity's "ease of purchase" relates to how simple it is to through the legal, regulatory, and administrative hoops necessary to make the acquisition.

Bhargavi (2014) revealed Investor trends and perceptions across the generations, as well as gender. Risk preferences and unwillingness to make risky judgments were lower in female and elderly investors. Males and young investors were also involved in making various investing decisions.

Goyal and Sharma (2014) found that a person's investment preference is greatly influenced by their familiarity with various investment options. Personal attributes have a considerable impact on an investor's investing choice in addition to knowledge.

Jagongo A. et al. (2014) revealed that many factors influenced an individual investor's choice of a company to invest in, including the company's standing and reputation in its industry, the share price, anticipated investor dividends, expected corporate earnings, and profit statements, and economic effects of the investments.

Jain (2014) showed that women, particularly, place high importance on predictability and security in their investments. Even if they differ in age and income, salaried investors prefer long-term investment options that are highly secure and rewarding regardless of their work or marital status.

Sireesha, P. & Laxmi, S. (2013) identified which investment avenues would be most popular with investors based on demographics. According to the findings, respondents' investment intentions were heavily influenced by their gender,

age, and social circle. Investors, on the other hand, were found to be cautious and less anxious.

Chakraborty, S. (2012) analyzed those Women and men investors differ in their savings goals, investment behaviors, and tastes. According to the findings, a variety of demographic criteria, such as ages, professions, and levels of income, had sway over investors' desire to save money. Women investors were shown to be more risk-averse than males but also tend to save more money when their income rises.

Dhar, P. & Dey, B. (2012) conducted psychological perceptions of investors' investment behaviors examined in a study including 82 participants. Researchers found that people who were optimistic and male investors preferred long-term investments in the study. Individuals' investing intentions were found to be heavily influenced by their level of trust in financial institutions.

Hossain & Nasrin (2012) According to a Bangladesh study, Investor retention is heavily influenced by a company's specific attributes and prestige, asset value, accounting records, company growth, media exposure, ownership structure, and the influence of individuals, as well as personal financial needs. These were the eight most significant factors. According to one study, elevated risk makes investments more in injustices to increase their rewards.

Khamees et al. (2010) conducted DCF (Discounted cash flow) and non-DCF approaches that were found to be used equally by the Jordan Industrial Corporation for appraising investment projects. The most common approach would be the PI, followed by the PBP, according to the finding. According to the survey results, respondents do not rely solely on one method. This study did not show that DCF or non-DCF cash flow methods were preferable to the other approaches, despite the data indicating that the PI technique was the most frequently employed, followed by the PBP (Payback period) method.

Singh & Jha (2009) discovered mutual funds' capacity to produce returns, liquidity, and security; investors were unaware of systematic investing programs (SIPs). Aging and earnings have an impact on investor preferences for mutual funds. While age had a considerable impact on mutual fund knowledge, neither gender had a significant impact. Investors between the ages of 20 and 30 preferred mutual funds.

3. Research Objectives

1. To study the effect of the global pandemic affecting investors investing decisions in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.
2. To determine the association between the age group and income on the amount invested before or during Covid - 19 outbreaks.
3. To investigate the psychological factors affecting investors' investing decisions in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.

4. Research Hypothesis

- **H1** : 'There is a significant impact of the global pandemic (covid-19) on Investors' Decision Making in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali'.

H0 : 'There is no significant impact of the global pandemic (covid-19) on Investors' Decision Making in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali'.

- **H2** : 'There is a significant association between the age group and income on the amount invested before or during Covid-19 outbreaks.'

H0 : 'There is no significant association between the age group and income on the amount invested before or during Covid-19 outbreaks.'

- **H3** : 'There is a significant impact of psychological factors on Investors' Decision Making in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.'

H0 : 'There is no significant impact of psychological factors on Investors' Decision Making in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.'

5. Research Methodology

Research technique refers to the framework that researchers utilize in their investigation. The primary data was acquired using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire with closed-ended questions. It suggests that the questions' answers were placed beforehand. These "five points (5 points for strong agreement, 4 points for agreement, 3 points for neutral (neither agree nor disagree), 2 points for disagreement, and 1 point for extreme disagreement)" also serve as scores for choosing the correct response. The self-administered questionnaires include two parts: one concentrates on demographic information and the other on behavioral factors, and each variable has its own set of closed-ended questions. The questionnaire was sent to 225 individuals who frequently

participate in the stock market, whether they are small/part-time investors or full-time investors. These investors were selected through a convenient sampling technique. The study area's major emphasis is the city of Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali. The investor's data were then evaluated using various statistical methods and approaches. Excel from Microsoft and SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) from IBM were used. These tools also used statistical tests, such as Mean, Standard Deviation, Correlation, and Regression, to examine the results.

Figure-1 : Research Framework

6. Result

Table-1 displays the demographic characteristics of the sample population according to gender, age, level of education, monthly income, investment type, and sample size. Table 1 shows that "out of 225 respondents, 71.10% are male and 28.90% are female; 20.90% are between the ages of 18 and 25; 38.20% are between the ages of 26 and 32; 29.80% are between the ages of 33 and 40; and 11.10% are at least 40 years old."

Objective-1 : To study the effect of the global pandemic affecting investors investing decisions in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.

Table-1 : Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

S No.	Demographic Characteristics	Category	N	%
1.	Gender	Male	160	71.10%
		Female	65	28.90%
2.	Age Group	18-25 years	47	20.90%
		26-32 years	86	38.20%
		33-40 years	67	29.80%
		Above 40 years	25	11.10%
3.	Education	High school or lower	65	28.90%
		Intermediate	72	32%
		Graduation	38	16.90%
		Masters	25	11.10%
		PHD	25	11.10%
4	Monthly income	Less than 20000	29	12.90%
		20000-40000	72	32.00%
		40001- 60000	84	37.30%
		More than 60000	40	17.80%
5.	Type of investor	Full time	68	30.20%
		Part-time	157	69.80%
6.	Investment Experience	less than 3 years	43	19.10%
		3-5 years	99	44.00%
		6-8 years	60	26.70%
		More than 8 years	23	10.20%

Source : Compiled by the Author.

Table-2 : Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.140 ^a	.019	.015	2.75715
a. Predictors: (Constant), Global Pandemic				

Table-2 shows that the R-value, which stands for the simple correlation, is 0.140, showing a very high correlation level and indicating how much of the overall variance in “Investing choice” can be accounted for by the independent variable.

Table-3 : ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33.691	1	33.691	4.432	.036 ^b
	Residual	1695.224	223	7.602		
	Total	1728.916	224			
a. Dependent Variable: Investing decision						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Global Pandemic						

The regression equation’s goodness-of-fit to the data is reported in the ANOVA table, which can be seen in Table-3. The regression model in this table predicts the dependent variable with high accuracy. It is concluded that there is a significant impact of the Global Pandemic on Investing decisions of investors as the significant value is smaller than 0.05.

Table-4 : Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.544	1.052		14.773	.000
	Global Pandemic	.152	.072	.140	2.105	.036
a. Dependent Variable: Investing decision						

The Coefficients Table-4 provides the necessary information regarding how effectively the independent variables impact the dependent variables. According to Table 4, the Global Pandemic greatly impacts investors' investing decisions as the significance value is smaller than 0.05.

Objective-2 : To determine the association between the age group and income on the amount invested before or during Covid-19 outbreaks.

- **Age group**

Table-5 : Descriptives

Descriptives								
Global Pandemic								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
18-25 years	47	13.6383	2.32590	.33927	12.9554	14.3212	9.00	18.00
26-32 years	86	14.1860	2.54610	.27455	13.6402	14.7319	9.00	19.00
33-40 years	67	14.9851	2.56723	.31364	14.3589	15.6113	8.00	20.00
Above 40 years	25	14.1600	2.59294	.51859	13.0897	15.2303	9.00	18.00
Total	225	14.3067	2.54411	.16961	13.9724	14.6409	8.00	20.00

Table-5 shows the Descriptive statistics regarding the data ("i.e., mean, standard deviation, and 95% confidence intervals for the dependent variable"). The mean of all the age groups (i.e., 18–25 years, 26–32 years, 33–40 years, and Over 40 years) ranged between 13.6383 to 14.9851.

Table-6 : ANOVA

ANOVA					
Global Pandemic					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	53.621	3	17.874	2.829	.039
Within Groups	1396.219	221	6.318		
Total	1449.840	224			

Table-6 displays the ANOVA findings, which may indicate a statistically significant difference between the groups or no difference at all. The p-value of 0.039 is much lower than the threshold of 0.05. Consequently, there is a statistically significant variation in the median time needed to solve the spreadsheet issue based on age and investment amount before and after the Covid - 19 pandemic.

- **Income**

Table-7 : Descriptives

Descriptives								
Global Pandemic								
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Less than 20000	29	14.1724	2.17237	.40340	13.3461	14.9987	10.00	17.00
20000-40000	72	14.9583	2.59163	.30543	14.3493	15.5673	8.00	19.00
40001- 60000	84	13.7619	2.57710	.28118	13.2026	14.3212	9.00	19.00
More than 60000	40	14.3750	2.44622	.38678	13.5927	15.1573	9.00	20.00
Total	225	14.3067	2.54411	.16961	13.9724	14.6409	8.00	20.00

Table-7 shows the Descriptive statistics regarding the data (“i.e., mean, standard deviation, and 95% confidence intervals for the dependent variable”). The mean of all the income (i.e., Less than 20000, 20000-40000, 40001- 60000, and more than 60000) ranged between 13.7619 to 14.9583.

Table-8 : ANOVA

ANOVA					
Global Pandemic					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	56.214	3	18.738	2.971	.033
Within Groups	1393.626	221	6.306		
Total	1449.840	224			

Table-8 displays the ANOVA findings, which may indicate a statistically significant difference between the groups or no difference at all. The p-value of

0.033 is much lower than the threshold of 0.05. Consequently, there is a statistically significant variation in the median time needed to solve the spreadsheet issue based on income and investment amount before and after the Covid-19 pandemic.

Objective-3 : To investigate the psychological factors affecting investors' investing decisions in Chandigarh, Panchkula, and Mohali.

Table-9 : Model Summary

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.136 ^a	.019	.014	2.75848
a. Predictors: (Constant), Psychological factors				

Table-9 shows that the R-value, which stands for the simple correlation, is 0.136, showing a very high correlation level and indicating how much of the overall variance in "Investing choice" can be accounted for by the independent variable.

Table-10 : ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32.058	1	32.058	4.213	.041 ^b
	Residual	1696.857	223	7.609		
	Total	1728.916	224			
a. Dependent Variable: Investing decision						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Psychological factors						

The regression equation's goodness-of-fit to the data is reported in the ANOVA table, which can be seen in Table-10. The regression model in this table predicts the dependent variable with high accuracy. It is concluded that there is a significant impact of psychological factors on Investing decision of investors as the significant value is smaller than 0.05

Table-11 : Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	15.672	1.017		15.417	.000
	Psychological factors	.147	.072	.136	2.053	.041

a. Dependent Variable: Investing decision

The Coefficients Table-11 provides the necessary information regarding how effectively the independent variables impact the dependent variables. According to Table 4, the psychological factors greatly impact the Investing decision of investors as the significance value is smaller than 0.05.

7. Conclusion

The COVID-19 epidemic has had a major financial impact. The vast population and the struggling economy, particularly the “financial sector”, have unsettled social estrangement & lockdown. Investors’ confidence in “mutual funds” & the “stock market” has been hit due to government actions like lockdowns and crashes. Today’s investors tend to be more “risk-averse” than in the past, preferring the security and steadiness of low-risk investments. Investors should also be familiar with Gold exchange-traded funds, stock market entry and exit points, and mutual fund schemes. According to a study, older investors may rely on their financial knowledge rather than a financial advisor to help them with their investments. “Mutual fund” groups & “policymakers” should also organize financial literacy initiatives in smaller communities, as evidenced by this study. Investors’ demographic characteristics (i.e., Income and Age) and psychological aspects such as (Overconfidence, Conservatism, Herding, and Availability Bias) also greatly affect investors’ investment choices, as does the worldwide pandemic (Covid-19). The entire debate of this research work was compiled to disperse information about the “Indian stock market” and its processes, determinants, and consequences from the perspective of the Psychological and personal (demographic) approach, as this provides a crucial means by which to comprehend the relationship between the global pandemic and long-term investment value.

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